

PSYCHOLOGICAL FIRST AID OF BATSTATEU LEMERY STUDENT ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In an academe, Psychological First Aid contributes substantially to assist those with emotional distress. Its goal is to be supportive with stress-related reactions, so the researchers prompted to assess the psychological first aid of BatState-U Lemery student organizations. To achieve the purpose, profile variables were identified in terms of age, sex, department, and college as well as the activities facilitated by student organizations that foster psychological first aid core values. Moreover, the effectiveness of the psychological first aid activities of the students' organization were also assessed in terms of contact and engagement, safety and comfort, stabilization, information gathering, current needs and concerns, practical assistance, connection with social support, information in coping and linkage with collaborative service. The significant difference on the respondent's assessment of the affected variables when grouped according to their profile were also determined. Specifically, this study utilized descriptive method research which was participated by 291 students of the said campus. The study utilized the sampling method of research and used Survey questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument through Google Forms. Data collected were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using statistical tools such as weighted mean and independent t-test. Findings revealed that majority of the respondents belonged to the age bracket of 20-22, females and from the College of Accountancy and Business Economics. Webinar is the activity of BatStateU Lemery student organizations that mostly fostered Psychological First Aid Core Values to the students while culminating activity is least fostered. All Psychological First Aid Core values are effectively used and fostered by the student organizations of BatStateU Lemery. Consequently, there is no significant relationship between the profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, and college department in the psychological first aid core values. Thus, a strategic plan for Student Organizations and Activities (SOA) was recommended to strengthen and foster Psychological First Aid to the students.

Keywords: Psychological First Aid, School Organization, student activities